

Synthesis of some New *N*-Naphthylquinoline and Quinazoline Derivatives

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Enaminones are versatile reagents for the synthesis of quinoline and pyrimidine derivatives^{1,2}. As a part of programme directed towards the synthesis of new suitably functionalised quinolines and quinazolines of potential biological activity³, we report here the possible utility of 3-naphthylaminocyclohexanone (2) with its bulky naphthyl moiety in the synthesis of *N*-naphthylquinoline and quinazoline ring systems.

Enaminone 2 was obtained (Scheme 1) from condensation of 5,5-dimethyl-1,3-cyclohexandione (1) with α -naphthylamine. Treatment of enaminone 2 with cinnamionitriles (3a-d) in presence of catalytic amount of triethylamine resulted in cycloaddition affording the quinolines (5a-d) presumably via Michael type product (4). ¹H nmr of 5a showed 4H-pyridine as a singlet at δ 4.7. Enaminonitrile 5a seemed to be a good starting material for direct annelation using simple reagent⁴. Thus, reaction of 5a with hydrazine hydrate furnished pyrazoloquinoline (6). Addition of 5a to benzoyl isothiocyanate (11a) gave quinolinopyrimidine (7) as a product of cycloaddition. Acylation of 5d with acetic anhydride in presence of catalytic amount of pyridine yielded quinolinopyrimidine (8). Condensation of 5a with semicarbazide hydrochloride gave semicarbazone (9). Oxidative cyclisation of 9 using selenium dioxide gave 1,2,3-selenadiazole (10). Enaminone 2 was reacted with aroyl isothiocyanate (11a-c) to give quinazolines (12a-c)². Condensation of 12a with hydrazine hydrate afforded pyrazoloquinoline (13).

Scheme 1

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Microanalyses were carried out at Microanalytical Centre, Cairo University. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian HA 100 (100 MHz) spectrometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer.

5,5-Dimethyl-3-(α -naphthylamino)cyclohexanone (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and α -naphthylamine (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 h. The solid obtained upon cooling was crystallised from aqueous methanol as yellow crystals (80%), m.p.155–57°; ν_{\max} 3 300–3 200 (NH), 1 650 cm^{-1} (CO).

2-Amino-4-aryl-3-cyano(carboxamido)-N(α -naphthyl)-7,7-dimethylhexahydroquinoline (5a-d): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol), appropriate cinnamionitrile (3; 0.01 mol) and triethylamine (3 drops) in ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 h. The solid obtained upon cooling was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals (yields 60–65%): 5a, m.p. 24–25°; ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH₂), 1 650 cm^{-1} (CO); δ 0.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.6–2.1 (4H, m, 2 \times CH₂), 4.0 (2H, s, NH₂), 4.7 (1H, s, pyridine), 7.2–7.8 (12H, m, ArH); b, 24–41°; c, 280°; d, 160°.

Pyrazoloquinoline (6): A mixture of 5a (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.025 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The solid obtained upon cooling was crystallised from methanol as colourless crystals (60%),

m.p. 255°, ν_{\max} 3 300–3 200 cm^{-1} (NH, NH_2).

Quinoline (7): A mixture of benzoyl isothiocyanate (4a; 0.01 mol) and 5a (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed for 1 h. The solid obtained upon pouring into water (20 ml) was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals (50%), m.p. 165–67°; ν_{\max} 3 300–3 200, 1 600, 1 650 cm^{-1} (CO).

Quinolinopyrimidine (8): A mixture of 5d (0.01 mol), acetic anhydride (0.01 mol) and pyridine (3 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The solid obtained upon pouring into HCl (50%; 5 ml) was crystallised from methanol as colourless crystals (60%), m.p. 230°; ν_{\max} 1 660, 1 645 cm^{-1} (CO).

Semicarbazone (9): To a solution of 5a (0.01) in ethanol (20 ml), a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (1.5 g) in water (4 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 1 h. The solid obtained after cooling was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, (70%), m.p. 170°; ν_{\max} 3 200 (NH_2), 2 215 (CN), 1 650 cm^{-1} (CO).

1,2,3-Selenadiazoloquinoline (10): To a solution of 9 (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml), selenium dioxide powder (0.01 mol) was added, and the mixture was warmed gently on a water-bath with stirring till the gas evolution ceased. The mixture was then filtered, solvent evaporated under the reduced pressure and the residue was crystallised from acetic acid as brown crystals (60%), m.p. 190–91°; ν_{\max} 3 200 (NH_2), 2 215 (CN), 840 cm^{-1} (C–Se–N); δ 0.8 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.0 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.7 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1–7.9 (10H, m, ArH).

1-Naphthyl-2-phenyl-5-oxoquinazoline-4-thione (12):

A mixture of benzoyl isothiocyanate (11a-c; 0.01 mol) and enamionone (2; 0.01 mol) in acetone (10 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The solid obtained upon pouring into water (10 ml) was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals (65%), 12a, m.p. 145–46°; b, 140–42°; c, 160–62°; δ 0.9 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.0 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.6–2.0 (4H, m, 2 × CH_2), 7.0–8.1 (12H, m, ArH).

Pyrazoloquinoline (13): A mixture of 12a (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mol) in methanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The solid obtained upon cooling was crystallised from methanol as colourless crystals (60%), m.p. 150–52°; ν_{\max} 1 580 cm^{-1} (C=N).

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